

STUDIES IN CARBOHYDRATES. PART VII. INVESTIGATION OF BAEL FRUIT (*Aegle Marmelos*) MUCILAGE

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The mucilage obtained as a white powder from *Aegle marmelos* has been investigated and found to be non-reducing in character, optically active ($[\alpha]_D^{27}, +22^\circ$) and possessing no acetyl or methoxyl group. It shows positive tests for galactan and pentosan. The hydrolysate of the mucilage shows the presence of galactose, arabinose and a trace of methylpentose. Methylated mucilage on hydrolysis has yielded four sugars, two of which, forming the major part, have been identified as 2:3:4:6-tetra-*O*-methyl- and 4:6 di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose. Chemical and physical characteristics have been studied with a view to ascertaining the structure of the mucilage.

Aegle marmelos (N. O. Rutaceae), commonly known as *Bael*, is valued in Ayurvedic medicine for dysentery and diarrhoea. A furocoumarin, marmelosin (Dixit and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1932, 9, 271), has been isolated from the fruit as an active constituent. The present work is concerned with the investigation of the mucilage from the fruit.

The mucilage is present in the fruits as a jelly, surrounding the seeds, and can be obtained as a white powder by precipitation with alcohol. It is a neutral polysaccharide which does not contain acetyl or methoxyl group (ash, 1.6% ; N, 1%). The mucilage, free from ash and nitrogen, has been obtained as a white powder by the modified procedure of Fraenkel and Jellinek (*Biochem. Z.*, 1927, 185, 392).

The purified mucilage is non-reducing having $[\alpha]_D^{27}, +22^\circ$ (*c*, 2% in water). It gave positive tests for galactan and pentosan and negative tests for ketoses, uronic acid and methylpentoses, though traces of methylpentoses were finally detected in the hydrolysate. The quantitative estimations of sugars gave 84.7% anhydrogalactan, 8.4% anhydropentosan and 2% methylpentosan.

The hydrolysate of the mucilage on chromatographic examination showed the presence of galactose, arabinose, and a trace of methylpentose corresponding to rhamnose. D-Galactose and L-arabinose were obtained in crystalline forms and were characterised by preparation of the usual derivatives. The mother-liquor gave strong tests for rhamnose, but it could not be obtained in a crystalline condition. Mild hydrolysis of the mucilage, under the conditions which have been found to hydrolyse the pentoses in furanose form only (White, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1507), failed to effect the complete rapture of arabinose from the mucilage, indicating that at least some part of arabinose must be present in the pyranose form.

Methylation of the purified mucilage, initially by dimethyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide and finally by Purdie's reagent, gave a methylated product {OMe, 39.6% ; $[\alpha]_D^{27}, -41^\circ$ (*c*, 2% in chloroform)}, which on hydrolysis yielded four sugars, two of which have been identified as 2:3:4:6-tetra-*O*-methyl- and 4:6 di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and found in the hydrolysate in approximately equimolecular proportions. The remaining two sugars were not examined as the quantities obtained were too small. However, the chromatographic studies indicate that at least one of them is an arabinose derivative.

The molecular weight of the purified mucilage was found to be 1364 (cryoscopically). This low molecular weight suggests that the methylpentose (2%) present may not probably be the constituent of the polysaccharide molecule. A molecule of the mucilage might be composed of 8 units of D-galactose and 1 unit of L-arabinose which requires 89.6% anhydrogalactan (found 84.7%) and 8.13% anhydropentosan (found 8.4%). Although the data cited in the present work do not lead to a definite structure of the mucilage due to the non-identification of arabinose derivative, it is evident from the relative proportion of galactose molecule and its derivatives that the mucilage is highly branched and possesses 1:2 and 1:3 linkages. The optical rotations of the mucilage and of its methylated derivative suggest β linkages. One out of several structures satisfying the above results is shown below.

Gal_p = D-galactopyranose.

(The position of arabinose unit is not decided.)

The results of the periodate oxidation are also in agreement with this type of structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of the Mucilage and Purification.—The fruits (20), each weighing on an average 400 g., were cut open in the middle and seeds encapped in the cavities were collected along with the mucilaginous coating. The jelly (500 c.c.) with the seeds was diluted with water (100 c.c.) and pressed through muslin. The filtrate was gradually added to ethanol (90%, 1.5 litres) when the mucilage precipitated as a sticky mass. On trituration with absolute alcohol, it formed a granular powder (yield 270 g.). The dry powder gave 1.6% ash which dissolved completely in dilute hydrochloric acid and showed the presence of Fe³⁺, Ca²⁺ and PO₄³⁻. It contained 1.1% nitrogen and did not show the presence of acetyl and methoxyl groups.

An aqueous solution of the mucilage, under the microscope, was found to be heterogeneous containing insoluble particles, the number of which was considerably lowered after filtering the solution three times (found: N, 0.6%). The mucilage, free from nitrogen and ash, was obtained by the following procedure. The mucilage (10 g.), dissolved in water (50 c.c.), was heated on a water-bath with barium hydroxide (5%, 50 c.c.) for 4 hours and then neutralised with requisite amount of sulphuric acid, and CO₂ was passed to precipitate the residual barium. The solution was filtered and the mucilage was precipitated by adding the filtrate to alcohol containing 1% HCl (1 litre). The precipitate was dissolved in water and reprecipitated by alcohol. Two to three similar treatments gave the mucilage as an amorphous powder. It was washed with ethyl alcohol till free from Cl⁻ (ash, negligible; N, nil).

The mucilage gave tests for galactan and pentosan and did not answer the tests for ketoses, uronic acid and methylpentoses, though the traces of methylpentoses were detected later. Pentoses and methylpentoses were estimated by A. O. A. C. methods, while galactose was estimated by hydrolysing the mucilage and preparing the galactose α -methylphenylhydrazone according to Hirst, Jones and Woods (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1048). The results of the estimation are given above. The molecular weight of the mucilage was found to be 1364 cryoscopically.

Hydrolysis of the Mucilage by 10% H₂SO₄.—The mucilage (10 g.) was dissolved in 10% H₂SO₄ (100 c.c.) and heated to 90°. The hydrolysis was followed polarimetrically as well as by finding the reducing power of the hydrolysate by Bertrand and Mohr's method, calculated as glucose. The reducing power and the rotations are given below.

TABLE I

Period (in hrs.)	1	2	3	4	5	
$[\alpha]_D^{27}$	...	+69°.5	+82°	+91°.5	+95°	+95°
Reducing power of the hydrolysate	Nil	49.6	62	89.2	94.3	94.3

The hydrolysate on neutralisation with barium carbonate was concentrated to a syrup which on chromatographic examination was found to contain three reducing sugars. The syrup on extraction with dry methanol left a residue (A), which was mainly galactose; the methanolic extract (B) was chromatographically found to contain arabinose and a methylpentose, probably rhamnose. The residue (A) on crystallisation gave pure crystalline D-galactose, m.p. and mixed m.p. 164°; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +80° (c, 2% in water). Its α -methylphenylhydrazone melted at 186°. The filtrate (B) on concentration gave white crystals of L-arabinose which were removed and purified by recrystallisation, m.p. and mixed m.p. 158°; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +105° (c, 2% in water). It gave a diphenylhydrazone, m.p. 201°. From the mother-liquor, rhamnose could not be obtained in a crystalline form; however, the mother-liquor gave positive Rosenthaler's test and the R_v value of the methylpentose present was identical with that of rhamnose.

Isolation of Galactan.—The mucilage (20 g.) was heated at 90° with 0.1N-H₂SO₄ (200 c.c.). The mixture became slightly reducing after 8 hours. The heating was continued and the reducing power estimated after 4 hours. It was found that the reducing power of the hydrolysate remained more or less constant after 24 hours. After hydrolysing the mucilage for 32 hours, the acid was neutralised by barium carbonate and the filtrate was added to ethanol (1.5 litres), when the degraded mucilage precipitated as a white solid. The chromatographic examination of the alcoholic extract showed the presence of galactose, arabinose and rhamnose. The degraded mucilage was freed of monosaccharides and was again hydrolysed, when galactose and arabinose were detected in the hydrolysate, indicating that the arabinose present in the mucilage was in the pyranose form.

Methylation of the Mucilage.—The mucilage (20 g.) was methylated 4 times at 30°, by adding dimethyl sulphate (300 c.c.) and NaOH (850 c.c., 30%) each time

during 7 hours and concentrating the solution to remove sodium sulphate. The partially methylated mucilage was dissolved in acetone and remethylated 3 times by the above procedure. The partially methylated product was dissolved in chloroform, washed with 20% sodium sulphate solution and was finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extract on removal of the solvent yielded a solid (19 g., OMe, 32%). It was further methylated twice by Purdie's reagent (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 1021) (found: OMe, 37.9%). Further treatment with Purdie's reagent did not increase the methoxyl content; yield 17.5 g.

Fractionation of the Methylated Mucilage.—The methylated mucilage was fractionated in chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) solvent system. The product was dissolved in chloroform and fractionally precipitated by adding petroleum ether. Four different fractions were collected (Table II).

TABLE II

Fraction No.	% OMe.	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$ ($c = 2\%$ in CHCl_3).	Yield.
I	35.0	$-38^{\circ}.1$	2.1 g.
II	36.6	$-38^{\circ}.3$	6.0
III	37.0	$-39^{\circ}.0$	6.2
IV	39.6	$-41^{\circ}.1$	2.3

All these fractions on hydrolysis gave the same pattern of reducing sugars on paper chromatograms; hence fraction IV was only examined further.

Hydrolysis of Fraction (IV).—Fraction IV (0.5 g.) was heated with 7% HCl-MeOH mixture (60 c.c.) in a sealed tube for 6 hours at 90°. It was then diluted with *N*-HCl (60 c.c.) and heated further for 3 hours. The hydrolysate was treated with silver carbonate, filtered and the filtrate was treated with hydrogen sulphide to remove silver ions, and again filtered. The filtrate on concentration under reduced pressure gave a syrup (0.45 g.) which showed the presence of four sugars on paper chromatograms. The syrup (0.4 g.) was separated on the cellulose column (60 × 5 cm) using benzene-ethanol-water (169:47:15; v/v; 1200 c.c.) as the eluting mixture. Fractions IV_a, IV_b, IV_c and IV_d were collected out of which IV_a and IV_b formed the major part of the syrup (about 80 to 85%), while IV_c and IV_d were in small quantities and were not examined.

Fraction IV_a: Identification of 2:3:4:6-Tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose.—The syrup had OMe, 46.96%; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+60^{\circ}.1$ (c , 2% in ethanol). On a paper chromatogram it ran side by side with the authentic specimen of 2:3:4:6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$) which requires Me, 52.1%; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, $+62^{\circ}.6$ (ethanol) (Irvine and Cameron, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 83, 1071), concluding that fraction IV_a (yield 0.18 g.) was 2:3:4:6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose. It was further confirmed by preparing its anilide, m.p. and mixed m.p. 194°. (Found: OMe, 39.6. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ requires OMe, 39.9%).

Fraction IV_b: Identification of 4:6-Di-O-methyl-D-galactose.—This syrup, on trituration with dry ether, gave white crystals (yield 0.16 g.), m.p. 161°; OMe (found) 41.6%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +97°.5 (*c.* 0.48% in water). It did not reduce Fehling's solution, indicating that the glycoside was formed during separation. It was further hydrolysed by 1*N*-HCl for 3 hours and worked up as described under the hydrolysis of fraction IV. The syrup, thus obtained, was reducing and it was crystallised from benzene-ethanol-water, m.p. 103°; OMe, 27%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +110° (*c.* 0.36% in water). The physical constants suggested that the sugar might be 2:4 di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose monohydrate (C₈H₁₆O₆·H₂O) which requires OMe, 27.4%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, +123° falling to +82° and m.p. 105° (Hirst and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1482). The crystalline sugar gave an anilide, m.p. 206°; OMe, 22.2%; N, 5.3%; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -169°.5 (*c.* 0.36% in pyridine) which confirmed the above inference as 2:4-di-*O*-methyl-D-galactose anilide (C₁₄H₂₁O₅N) which requires OMe, 21.9%; N, 5.0% and possesses m.p. 207°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -174° (*c.* 0.35% in pyridine) (Hirst and Jones, *loc. cit.*).

Periodate Oxidation of the Mucilage.—The dry mucilage (0.4614 g.) was dissolved in distilled water (65 c.c.) and sodium metaperiodate (35 c.c., 0.2*M*) was added to it. The oxidation was carried out for 16 hours when it was found to be complete. The mucilage (360 g.) consumed two molecules of sodium metaperiodate and liberated one molecule of formic acid.